

A NOTE ON THE USE OF ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ACIDIMETRY AND ALKALIMETRY.

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In a previous communication (Roy, *J. Indian chem. Soc.* 1936, 13, 436) the applicability of adsorption indicators in acidimetry and alkalimetry has been described where fluorescein was used as the adsorption indicator in conjunction with lead nitrate. In the present paper attempts have been made to describe the use of fluorescein as an adsorption indicator in conjunction with stannous chloride.

A known volume of standard hydrochloric or sulphuric acid (strength not less than $N/15$) was taken in a conical flask to which a few drops of fluorescein (0.5% solution of sodium fluoresceinate) and traces of stannous chloride were added and the mixture titrated with caustic soda or sodium carbonate. The end-point was marked by the sudden disappearance of the dull-green colour of the solution and consequent development of a distinct yellowish red colour. The solution becomes turbid at the same time. Eosin may be used instead of fluorescein in which case the colour changes from a dull red to a brilliant turbid violet.

The strengths of the alkali and the acid determined in this way were compared with those obtained by titration with methyl orange as indicator and two results were found to be concordant in moderate dilution, as will be evident from the following table.

Conc. of acid or alkali (approx.).	Vol. of alkaline soln. required for a known vol. of acid.	Vol. of alkaline soln. for the same vol. of acid.
	(Methyl orange)	(SnCl_2 & fluorescein or eosin)
$N/2$	15.40	15.40
$N/5$	15.50	15.50
$N/8$	15.45	15.45
$N/10$	18.50	18.55
$N/15$	18.50	18.60

The best results were obtained with $N/2$ to $N/10$ solution. In dilute solutions the results slightly differ from those obtained by using methyl orange. This is due to the fact that stannous chloride gives a weak acid reaction in solution and hence a larger volume of alkali will be necessary to effect the desired colour change. For the same reason acetic acid can not be determined accurately by this method. Large neutral salts effect the colour change to a considerable degree.

The mechanism of the reaction may be explained in the following way,—when all the acid is neutralised, the excess drop of alkali hydroxide or carbonate reacts with stannous chloride forming stannous hydroxide, on which are adsorbed stannous and fluorescein ions from the solution with the development of a pink colour on the surface of the precipitate.

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